

THE IMPORTANCE OF EFFECTIVE TEACHER'S SPEECH IN THE CLASSROOM

Kakharova Shohsanam

Fergana State University, teacher
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ABSTRACT

This article provides detailed information about the importance of the teacher's speech in improving the effectiveness of the lesson, the requirements and methods for effective and meaningful speech.

In general, a teacher's speech can refer to any spoken communication that a teacher delivers to their students. This could include lectures, discussions, presentations, or any other form of verbal communication that takes place in a classroom or educational setting.

According to the S.D.Yakusheva, speech culture – a culture of personality that develops on the basis of objectively existing links between language and cognitive processes, suggesting a sense of style, taste and erudition developed. [1, 59].

The importance of using vocal features and head gestures in increasing students' motivation and enhancing their

There are several important factors to consider when analyzing a teacher's speech. These might include:

1.Clarity - how clear and understandable is the teacher's speech? Do they use complex vocabulary or technical terms that might be difficult for students to understand?

One of the key factors in effective teacher's speech is clarity. A teacher who speaks clearly and uses language that is appropriate for the students' level of understanding is more likely to be successful in conveying their message. This is particularly important for students who are learning a new language or who have limited prior knowledge of the subject matter.

Linguist S.Jalilov emphasizes that clarity is of two kinds: clarity of object and clarity of concept. If the speaker knows well the subject of the speech, chooses appropriate words for it and assigns tasks corresponding to the meanings of the words, then the speech will be clear.[2,21]

2.Tone – what is the teacher's tone of voice? Are they authoritative, friendly, enthusiastic, or some other tone? How does their tone affect the students' engagement and comprehension of the material?

Another important factor is tone. A teacher's tone of voice can affect how students perceive the material and their level of engagement. A friendly, enthusiastic tone can make the

material seem more interesting and relevant, while an authoritative tone can help establish the teacher's credibility and expertise. The tone of the speech should be appropriate for the subject matter and the audience, and should be used to create a positive learning environment.

3. Structure – how well-organized is the teacher's speech? Is there a clear introduction, body, and conclusion? Do they use clear transitions to move from one point to another?

Structure is another key element of effective teacher's speech. A well-organized speech should have a clear introduction, body, and conclusion, with each section building on the previous one. Clear transitions should be used to move from one point to another, and visual aids such as diagrams or slides can be helpful in reinforcing key concepts.

4. Engagement – how engaged are the students during the teacher's speech? Do they seem interested and attentive, or are they bored or distracted?

Engagement is also an important factor in effective teacher's speech. A teacher who is able to keep students engaged and interested in the material is more likely to be successful in helping them learn. Storytelling, using examples or anecdotes, and incorporating group discussions or activities can help make the material more relatable and memorable for students.

5. Effectiveness – how effective is the teacher's speech in achieving its goals? Does it convey the intended information clearly and effectively, or are there areas where it could be improved?

Finally, the effectiveness of a teacher's speech can be evaluated by how well it achieves its goals. A speech that effectively conveys the intended information and helps students understand and retain the material is more likely to be successful. Teachers should be open to feedback and willing to adjust their approach to better meet the needs of their students.

To conclude, a teacher's speech is a powerful tool for conveying information and engaging students in the learning process. By focusing on factors such as clarity, tone, structure, engagement, and effectiveness, teachers can improve the quality of their speeches and enhance their students' learning experiences. An effective teacher's speech can make all the difference in helping students achieve their educational goals.

There are many ways which can help to organize effective speech in the classroom. As we know, the purpose of a teacher's speech can vary depending on the context and subject matter. For example, a speech in a science class might aim to explain complex scientific concepts to students, while a speech in a language class might focus on helping students improve their language skills. Understanding the specific purpose of a teacher's speech can help students better engage with the material and retain important information.

Non-verbal communication can also play an important role in a teacher's speech. This includes factors like body language, facial expressions, and gestures. A teacher's non-verbal cues can help convey meaning, emphasize important points, and create a sense of rapport and connection with students.

Different teaching styles can influence the way a teacher delivers a speech. For example, a teacher who uses a more traditional, lecture-based approach might rely heavily on verbal communication, while a teacher who uses a more interactive, student-centered

approach might incorporate more group discussions, activities, or visual aids into their speech.

A teacher's speech can have a powerful impact on student motivation and engagement. When students feel that a teacher is passionate, knowledgeable, and invested in the subject matter, they are more likely to feel motivated to learn and participate in class. On the other hand, a teacher who delivers a speech in a monotonous or disengaged manner can quickly lose students' attention and interest.

The use of storytelling can be an effective tool for engaging students in a teacher's speech. By using anecdotes or examples to illustrate key concepts, a teacher can make the material more relatable and memorable for students. Storytelling can also help create a sense of connection between the teacher and the students, which can increase their motivation to learn.

In addition to the content of a teacher's speech, the delivery can also be important. A teacher who speaks too quickly or too slowly, for example, may be difficult for students to understand. Similarly, a teacher who speaks in a monotone voice can make the material seem uninteresting or unimportant. Using pauses, inflection, and emphasis can help convey meaning and make the speech more engaging.

A teacher's speech can be delivered in a variety of formats, including in-person lectures, online videos, or live webinars. Each format has its own advantages and challenges. For example, an in-person lecture allows for more face-to-face interaction with students, while an online video can be watched at a student's own pace. Teachers may need to adjust their delivery style depending on the format they are using.

One challenge of delivering a teacher's speech is making sure that all students are able to understand the material, regardless of their individual learning styles or abilities. Some students may be visual learners who benefit from diagrams or visual aids, while others may be auditory learners who benefit from hearing the material spoken aloud. A teacher who is able to accommodate different learning styles can increase the effectiveness of their speech.

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